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TEMPLATE FORM ON FACULTY FULL-BLOWN PROPOSAL AND FINAL IMRAD MANUSCRIPT

Title

Bridging Cultures, Expanding Horizons: Surfacing the Impact of Inbound and Outbound Mobility on Learning - Onward to a Robust Institutional Plan

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Abstract

Internationalization (IZN) is one of the growing parameters in gauging the societal impact of higher education institutions globally. This paradigm shift is a response to the constant and unpredictable change that has confronted humanity in recent years, challenging the traditional role of education in this rapidly changing world. The impact of education is put in the spotlight, and education experts and administrators are urged to reinvent strategic goals and curricula so that learners gain the global competencies necessary to navigate globally. Many of the world's leading policymakers have recognized the critical role of internationalization in achieving quality and excellence through education. The United Nations incorporated partnerships (SDG 17) in its sustainable development goals by 2030. The World University Rankings for Innovation (WURI) integrated student mobility as a category in measuring a university's real impact on society and industry. Hence, internationalization implies that higher education institutions establish relevant partnerships with external networks to foster an atmosphere of openness, participate in various mobility programs that allow their students and staff to appreciate and respect cultural differences, and collaborate with partners in solving humanity's global problems. For IZN to be effective, the participants must be impacted first. There is a dearth of research on this topic. Hence, this study examined participants' lived experiences in inbound and outbound mobility at Saint Mary's University (SMU). Using the phenomenological approach as a research design, the study explored the experiences of the participants during the mobility programs, how their experience impacted them, how they made use of their immersion in giving meaning to their education, and how they utilized their learnings in making an impact on the University and society. Based on the results,

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internationalization contributed to the global mobility participants' personal and professional growth. The results add value to the University's goal of leveling up its culture of quality and excellence through internationalization.

A. Introduction

Internationalization (IZN) has gained popularity in education over the past decades (Bedenlier & Zawacki-Richter, 2015) as global policymakers started using it as an index in assessing the fundamental contributions of education to society. Internationalization has become a key strategic priority of many universities worldwide (Robson, 2017) and has become a common theme in higher education discourse in recent years (Tasci, et al., 2022). The World University Rankings for Innovation (WURI) included student mobility as one of the 13 categories a higher education institution must excel in to be considered relevant, innovative, and significant (WURI, 2024). For mobilities to become possible, partnerships between or among parties must be forged and formalized through mutually beneficial agreements. These partnerships are necessary to articulate the responsibilities of all parties involved and to ensure that goals are aligned. It is therefore not a surprise when, in 2015, the United Nations included Partnership for the Goals (SDG 17) as one of the 17 SDGs to which all countries - developed and developing - in a global partnership must respond (<https://sdgs.un.org>, 2024). The UN sees the importance of international alliances in achieving sustainable development. After all, we live on one planet, and working with one another is necessary to achieve progress, clarity, and unity of direction. The importance of collaboration is also recognized by The Times Higher Education (THE) Impact Rankings. International outlook is one of the five performance indicators for which universities across the globe are rated. The other four areas are teaching, research environment, and industry ([timeshighereducation.com](https://www.timeshighereducation.com), 2024). In this context, international outlook pertains to the "ability of a university to attract undergraduates, postgraduates and faculty from all over the planet" as a key element to its success on the world stage ([timeshighereducation.com](https://www.timeshighereducation.com), 2024).

Internationalization is an essential component for the acquisition of global competencies needed to advance globally. Hence, many countries have integrated internationalization policies and practices in their HEIs (Robiños & Alcazaren, 2023). Buckner, et al. (2020) emphasized that one of the most significant justifications for internationalization is that it would help to improve intercultural understanding, global consciousness, and global citizenship.

Internationalization is often associated with physical mobility and high financial costs to make border transfer possible. It means that mobility is still the dominant factor in internationalization policies worldwide (de Wit, 2020). This view often discourages students with fewer opportunities even to begin exploring what internationalization has in store for them, despite its potential to develop significant global competencies. This can be considered one of the challenges of internationalization. It is, therefore, important to weigh the benefits and challenges of internationalization among participants who have engaged in global mobilities to assess its contribution to the development of the participants and the achievement of the goals of HEIs. This is especially true as the internationalization of

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higher education is entering a new phase. A move from internationalization overseas, which focuses on a small elite of mobile students, faculty, administrators, and programs, to internationalization at home for all students, faculty, and administrators is more important than ever (de Wit & Deca, 2020).

This study explored participants' lived experiences in inbound and outbound global mobility to revitalize the strategic internationalization plan of Saint Mary's University. It examined how education done outside the confines of the school borders – not just the classroom per se - has impacted the lives of its participants and the university. Furthermore, it explored how global mobility has been providing a different route to learning where learners and teachers gain practical knowledge from first-hand experiences by immersing themselves in diverse cultures, practices, strategies, and technologies to enrich a priori knowledge.

B. RRL and RS of Major Concepts / Variables

Internationalization in HEIs

There are many definitions of internationalization (IZN), but the most commonly cited definition was that of De Wit, et al., 2015 (in de Wit, 2020):

The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions, and delivery of post-secondary education, to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff and to make a meaningful contribution to society."

The definition above emanates from the generally accepted definition of Knight (2008, in de Wit, 2020), who forwarded the idea that IZN is the process of integrating an international and intercultural dimension in the delivery of post-secondary education. This implies that internationalization focuses on the higher education level, probably because students at this stage are more mature and more likely to be independent, moving across borders. The definition above also implies that internationalization efforts are intentional or purposeful, meaning that internationalization goals are anchored on achieving carefully established goals of mutual benefits for partners.

Hence, the word internationalization is often associated with linkages, global partnerships, mobilities, or anything that involves networking with other organizations (Robson, 2017) to widen access to new trends and promote openness with new ideas.

Internationalization Benefits to HEIs

Many studies pointed out why HEIs must invest in internationalization. For one, it elevates the University's culture of quality through higher points in university rankings. HEIs whose IZN endeavors are well supported often get favorable ratings in international rankings, thus, elevating the HEI's status as a world-class educational institution. The execution of strategies for internationalizing education has been positively perceived as a contributing factor toward quality culture in teaching and learning, and leadership and management (Robiños & Alcazaren, 2023).

Second, global mobilities foster an atmosphere of openness where participants are exposed to new ideas, cultures, practices, and even technology. New learnings acquired

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from these engagements and experiences may be shared with the home HEIs. Hence, every IZN plan must come with a dissemination plan, where participants are encouraged to echo what was learned to a greater number of participants. The dissemination plan may come in the form of a new teaching technique, a new student project, or the integration of an innovative practice. These new practices often lead to useful innovations that greatly impact society, which is a measure of real educational impact.

Third, global engagement and partnerships lead to a more united world where people get to understand and respect each other amid cultural diversity. It is a recognition that no culture is above the other, and world peace and unity are only achieved through partnerships that promote mutually beneficial interests. In the study conducted by Bedenlier and Richter (2015) on the internationalization of higher education and its impacts, they identified three categories of impacts: individual, institutional, and global. This means that internationalization efforts can impact the participants personally, the institution, and the society.

Internationalization and Global Competences

Higher education institutions all over the world have incorporated internationalization in their strategic plans as an important component of achieving a culture of quality and excellence. This paradigm shift is a recognition of the changing landscape of the evolving objectives of higher education institutions. According to the World University Ranking and Innovation (WURI), a leading ranking organization that pioneers the assessment of HEI impacts, universities must foster real-world impact and address societal needs to maintain relevance (WURI, 2024).

One way to measure real-world impact, according to WURI, is to assess HEI's student support mobility and openness to promote the sharing of knowledge. Many international ranking organizations have integrated internationalization endeavors as a key result area in rating organizations. The Times Higher Education (THE) Impact Rankings assesses universities against the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), one of which is Partnership for the Goals (SDG 17), which emphasizes global partnerships.

In the Philippines, local accrediting bodies have also embraced the significance of IZN in assessing the performance of HEIs. For example, the Commission of Higher Education has included global mobility as a parameter in evaluating both public and private HEIs.

Aside from the role IZN plays in measuring an HEI's culture of quality, many studies have been conducted citing the benefits that students, staff, and faculty members alike gain from internationalization endeavors. In the study by Guo and Guo in 2017, among 26 international students in Canada, the students reported that internationalization gave them a positive experience for academic and personal growth. This means that they found their experience outside their respective home countries beneficial in enhancing their education. Their experience has also improved their social skills through their interaction with students of various cultural backgrounds, thus contributing to their personal growth. It is not surprising, then, that one manifestation of the growing interest in internationalization

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is the increasing number of international students. In Canada, for instance, the number of international students in Canadian universities rose to 11% in 2014 (CBIE, 2015 in Guo and Guo, 2017), where international students reported that internationalization gave them a positive experience for academic and personal growth (Guo and Guo, 2017).

Internationalization Challenges

De Wit (2020) posited how some internationalization trends have changed over the years. There is an increasing interest in internationalizing the curriculum at home instead of physical mobility, which is often focused on the elite due to the cost of mobility programs. The motivation for internationalization is not just rankings but also integrating international dimensions in quality assurance mechanisms in tertiary education.

Other challenges include high cost and a lack of focus or direction in some global mobilities. These challenges raised concerns about equity of access to international opportunities (Robson, 2017).

The study conducted by Guo and Guo (2017) enumerated several persistent problems, including a neoliberal approach that treats internationalization as a marketing strategy, limited internationalization of the curriculum, and gaps between the internationalization policy and the experience of international students. The finding implies some mismatch in the direct experiences of the participants during the mobility program with the policies embedded in partnership agreements. Similar results were revealed by Kondakci, Van den Broeck, and Yildirim (2008), whose study found a dissonance between policymakers and implementers in internationalization activities. The reviewed studies and literature provided a framework for this current study, which examined the lived experiences of participants in inbound and outbound global mobilities and how their participation in internationalization initiatives has impacted them, their education, and the university.

C. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework on which this study is anchored is De Wit et al.'s (2015, in De Wit, 2020) framework of what internationalization should be. They defined internationalization this way:

“The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff and to make a meaningful contribution to society.”

The definition implies that every internationalization activity is purposeful or intentional, happens at the post-secondary level, and contributes to societal development. Since this present study was also about the impact of internationalization, it is anchored on the three categories of IZN impacts: individual level, institutional level, and global level. These categories were identified by Bedenlier and Richter (2015).

D. Conceptual and Analytical Framework

The study surfaced the lived experiences of inbound and outbound student mobility participants for the last three school years (SYs 2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025) based on their views about internationalization, the impact of their experiences during their participation, and the perceived contribution of their experience at the individual level, institutional level, and global level.

The results may add value to the University's goal of leveling up its culture of quality and excellence through internationalization.

E. Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

Generally, the study surfaced the lived experiences of inbound and outbound student mobility participants of SMU for the last three school years (SYs 2022-2023, 2023-2024, 2024-2025) after lifting travel restrictions due to the pandemic. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What does internationalization mean to inbound and outbound global mobility participants?
2. How do inbound and outbound global mobility participants view their experiences on internationalization?
3. How do inbound and outbound global mobility participants view the contribution of their experience to the University's culture of quality?

Methodology

A. Design

The study used a descriptive method of research. The design is phenomenological since it explored the participants' lived experiences in inbound and outbound global mobilities. Research that utilizes a phenomenological approach focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group (Tasci, 2022). The phenomenological study design was determined to be best suited for examining in detail the perspectives of stakeholders engaged in internationalization (Creswell, 2013, in Tasci, 2022). In-depth qualitative

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interviews have been shown in previous studies to be efficient tools for identifying the similarities and differences in internationalization experiences, cultural views, and practices of the faculty between two countries (Rubin & Rubin, 1995; Tasci, 2022).

B. Locale

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University (SMU), a private university in Cagayan Valley, Philippines. It can be said that SMU is one of the pioneers of internationalization in Region 2. Its internationalization initiatives include several partnerships with HEIs and organizations in Asia, Europe, and America as early as 2012. Notable partners include two universities in Europe – Howest University of Applied Sciences and Vives University of Applied Sciences – which are part of the bigger network called Synergy Program that started in 2016. SMU has an active network with ASEAN universities through the SEA-Teacher Project, where exchange student-teachers have regularly visited each other's universities for teaching immersion since 2017. Work and academic immersion programs and on-the-job training in Hospitality Management and Tourism, Forensic Science, Pharmacy, and Medical Laboratory Science have also been conducted with partners abroad.

C. Participants and Sample

A total of 63 global mobility participants from SY 2022-2023 to SY 2024-2025 participated in the study. Out of the 63 participants, 21 were male and 42 were female, and 24 were inbound student mobility participants and 39 were outbound student mobility participants. The youngest was 16 and the oldest was 25.

The participants were recruited based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

1. Those who participated in physical mobility programs of the University, regardless of the length of the activity, from SY 2022-2023 to SY 2024-2025; and
2. Currently enrolled or graduated college students.

The exclusion criteria are:

1. College students who attended mobility programs not facilitated by the University;
2. Those who attended online mobility programs, and
3. Basic education students

D. Instrument(s)

An in-depth written interview guide was used to gather data. In-depth qualitative interviews have been proven effective in bringing out participants' lived experiences. In-depth qualitative interviews have been shown in previous studies to be efficient tools for identifying the participants' similarities and differences in internationalization experiences, cultural views, and practices (Rubin & Rubin, 1995; Tasci, 2022). Document scanning was also done to cross-check the university's internationalization data.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

First, document scanning of narrative reports was done to ensure that the right participants were invited to participate in the study. These data were available at the SMU Promotions, External Relations, and Internationalization Office. Second, the names of participants were summarized, and an Informed Consent Form was administered to them online to ensure the voluntary nature of their participation. Third, an online written interview, which took the participants around 20-30 minutes to answer, was conducted through Google Forms from March 21 to April 7, 2025.

F. Treatment of Data

The data were treated thematically, which is a common treatment for phenomenological studies. Specifically, descriptive phenomenology with Colaizzi's method was used, as described by Gumarang et al. (2021). Specifically, each transcript was reviewed and reread to get a sense of the overall content and extract significant and recurring remarks, words, or phrases about the topic under investigation from each record. These statements were recorded, and meanings were formulated from these significant statements. After, the formulated meanings were sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes.

G. Ethical Considerations

The study was submitted to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB), Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, for assessment and approval, and is compliant with all ethical procedures as evidenced by the ethical clearance from the University's ethical board.

Results and Discussions

Meaning of Internationalization to Global Mobility Participants

To fully realize the goals of internationalization in higher education, global mobility participants must have a clear definition of internationalization. When asked about the meaning of internationalization to them, the following four themes surfaced:

Meaning of internationalization / global mobility

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Learning Opportunity	Opportunity, enhance skills/experience Learning a new language, culture, and global competencies	16
2. Building Connection	Build connection, bridge gaps/culture Opens doors to friendships Creating meaningful connections	17
3. Cultural Exchange	Exchange of culture, adapting to different languages, and exchanging cultures	16
4. Global affiliations	Affiliation, going global, expanding beyond borders, shrinking/ breaking boundaries	14
Total		63

First, global mobility participants see internationalization as a learning opportunity. This learning spectrum encompasses learning new languages, skills, cultures, and international competencies. Apparently, the participants associate the meaning of internationalization with opening doors for them to nurture themselves and their experiences. Second, internationalization means building connections. The participants see internationalization as an avenue to strengthen connections among people of different cultural backgrounds. It is a means of creating meaningful connections to bridge cultural differences. Third, internationalization means cultural exchange. It includes understanding and appreciating different cultural perspectives and adapting to practices different from their own. These practices include communication nuances, learning methodologies, and lifestyle differences. Fourth, the participants associate internationalization with global affiliations or a means of harmonizing best practices to break global boundaries. It means that the participants see internationalization as unifying people and nations.

It is interesting to note similarities between the definitions of internationalization by global mobility participants and the definition posited by Knight (2008, in de Wit, 2020). Knight emphasized the meaningful contribution of internationalization to society, which was validated by the responses from the participants who saw internationalization as a means to expand learning and to build connections and affiliations through cultural exchange. All these contribute to the individual's holistic development and becoming a functional member of society. Hence, internationalization is associated with linkages, global partnerships, mobilities, or networking with other organizations (Robson, 2017).

The above definitions of internationalization were further supported by the participants' motivations for joining global mobility activities, as shown below.

Motivation for joining global mobility

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Expand horizon	Gain experience, broaden horizons, explore the world, enrich knowledge, and personal and professional progress/growth	45
2. Meeting new people	Meeting new people, building new relationships, socializing/interacting with others, connecting with other people	9
3. Platform for discussion of solutions to global issues	Improve the country's lifestyle Advocates of social issues like climate change Discuss global concerns and solutions, SDGs A platform to discuss global concerns	5
4. Curiosity	Curious about the world, comparing differences, influenced by others, and heard it from a friend	4
Total		63

The participants' first motivation for joining global mobility activities is to expand their horizons. There is a burning desire on the part of the participants to broaden their

horizons and learn new things, whether improving their English skills or professional development. They wanted to step out of their comfort zone for personal progress and professional development. Second, they wanted to meet new people and develop friendships and connections. It reflects man's social nature, who finds life's meaning through communion with others. Third, the participants were motivated to join global mobility activities because they saw it as a platform for discussing solutions to global issues. This means that young people are aware of global concerns and recognize the power of international exchanges in finding solutions to global issues. The fourth motivation is out of curiosity. The participants heard about internationalization from their friends, so they became curious and joined. They were also curious about other countries, which is not surprising, especially since the Philippines is geographically isolated from its neighboring countries. This geographical position limits interaction with neighboring countries, leading to curiosity about what is on the other side.

These narratives were also revealed in the study of Guo and Guo (2017), where international students reported that internationalization gave them a positive experience for academic and personal growth.

Gains and Pains of Internationalization as Viewed by Global Mobility Participants

When asked how they view their global mobility experience, the participants shared their gains and pains during the exchange. Four themes emerged under gains, while three themes emerged under pains or challenges, as follows:

Gains from the global mobility experience

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Personal and academic growth	Gained new knowledge, skills, teaching experience, and improved communication skills Self-discovery/independence, developed confidence, academic exposure/exchange	38
2. Established new friendships	Gained friendships and bonding Network, connection, meeting new people	9
3. Cultural awareness and appreciation	Gained a more profound understanding /appreciation of different cultures A deeper understanding of how people from diverse backgrounds think and live	9
4. Flexibility	Learned to be flexible, resilient, and adaptable	4
No answer		3
Total		63

The gains from joining global mobility activities include personal and academic growth, establishing new friendships, cultural awareness and appreciation, and flexibility. This result was supported by the themes established for motivations in joining internationalization, which included expanding horizons and meeting new people as reasons for joining global mobility activities. The result also implies that the participants

see the positive impact of their internationalization experience on their personal and professional growth and development.

The result above supports the study conducted by Bedenlier and Richter (2015) on the internationalization of higher education and its impacts, categorized into three, namely individual, institutional, and global. This means that internationalization efforts can impact the participants personally, the institution, and the society, as revealed in the present study. If there are gains, there are also challenges, with the following themes:

Challenges of doing global mobility

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Samples
1. Language barrier	Language barrier, to do everything in English, difficulty of using a second language	16
2. Cultural adaptation	Adjustment, culture shock, cultural differences / educational setting, adjusting to the practices of the local community (road signs, modes of transport, food, and taking photos)	15
3. Personal struggles	Financial struggle to sustain IZN needs (food, water, travel expenses), lack of support for IZN, homesickness, and time management	6
No challenge / No answer		26
Total		63

Based on the participants' responses, they were most challenged by language barriers, cultural adaptation, and other personal struggles. Apparently, the language barrier is a common challenge among the participants. The language adapted as a means of communication in these global mobility activities is English, which is considered the international language. None of the participants is a native speaker of English, and this is where the challenge came from. The effective use of a language includes not just a wide range of vocabulary but a deep understanding of language semiotics. Problems like miscommunication, lack of vocabulary, and difficulty expressing thoughts and feelings happen. Another challenge is cultural adaptation. While cultural exchange was mentioned as a motivation for joining global mobility activities, the participants cited that adapting to another culture could be challenging. These challenges include culture shock and time in adjusting to the practices of the local community, such as road signs, modes of transport, food, and attitudes toward foreigners. Another challenge includes personal struggles, such as financial and a lack of support from expected support groups like family and school administration. This is not surprising since global mobility entails movement across borders, which always requires costs (de Wit, 2020).

Similarly, one study (Guo and Guo, 2017) revealed persistent problems in internationalization, including a neoliberal approach that treats internationalization as a marketing strategy, limited internationalization of the curriculum, and gaps between the internationalization policy and the experience of international students. It implied some mismatch in the direct experiences of the participants during the mobility program with

the policies embedded in partnership agreements (Guo and Guo, 2017). Similar results were revealed by Kondakci, Van den Broeck, and Yildirim (2008), whose study found a dissonance between policymakers and implementers in internationalization activities. It is essential, therefore, to review the alignment between partnership agreements and the perceived gains and challenges experienced by the global mobility participants.

When asked what school services they appreciate the most, five themes emerged.

School services appreciated by global mobility participants

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Support from global mobility organizers	Help from supervisors, availability of principal/ AFS coordinators, PERIO, and organizing departments	29
	Availability of financial assistance, Erasmus+	
	Organized activities for IZN, orientation programs, a tour around Bayombong, road trip	
2. Presence of Buddies and Student Volunteers	Buddies are just a call away, language support Student organizers/volunteer groups	12
	Welcoming and friendly environment Hospitable, kind community	
3. Non-academic mentorship	Career guidance, mentoring, and networking services	17
	Comfortable, clean, safe, dormitory facilities, counselling services, mental health resources	
No Answer		5
Total		63

The school services the participants appreciated the most were support from global mobility organizers, buddies/student volunteers, and non-academic support. The participants appreciated the presence of internationalization activities, such as Erasmus+ and ComMTECH, and how the organizers carry these out. They cited that the departmental supervisors and mentors were always available and approachable to assist and give tips regarding academic concerns. They also noted the activities organized by the internationalization office as a source of support, such as the pre-departure orientation, a tour around the campus and town, and other administrative support. The participants also appreciated the presence of buddies or student volunteers. The availability of buddies provided much-needed support for the participants to integrate into the local culture. There was less of a social barrier since the buddies were students and of the same age as the participants, so they could better express their needs to them. This relationship has created a more welcoming environment for the participants. Other non-academic support services were also appreciated, such as career guidance, counseling services, mental health resources, linkages, and the presence of clean dormitories and canteens. These support services were essential in ensuring that the participants had a holistic academic experience. These are reasons why there is a growing interest in internationalization globally, as shown

in the study in Canada, where the number of international students in Canadian universities rose to 11% in 2014 (CBIE, 2015, in Guo and Guo, 2017).

Contribution of Internationalization to the University's Culture of Quality as Viewed by Global Mobility Participants

Through their participation in global mobility activities, the participants see themselves as a cultural bridge, agents of change, and internationalization advocates in the university. These three roles emerged when the participants were asked about the contribution of their internationalization experience to the university's culture of quality.

How global mobility participants perceive their role in the university

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Cultural Bridge	Assistance that can help global mobility participants navigate the challenges, inspiration to other mobility participants, a bridge between cultures, and people, a cultural bridge	30
2. Agent of Change	Provide an assessment tool for a bullying program, an agent of change, and a contribution to the improvement of services, awareness of advocacies/ improvement of the country/university, and improvement of self	18
3. Internationalization advocate	Help in promoting IZN to other students IZN spokesperson, ambassador of cultural exchange and academic collaboration	9
No answer		6
Total		63

As a cultural bridge, the participants saw themselves as a bridge between cultures after their global mobility participation. They are eager to share their experience with other students at home so that others would also appreciate cultures other than their own. They believe that future participants could navigate internationalization more easily by being a cultural bridge. As agents of change, the participants saw their internationalization experience as a means to introduce change and improve standard practices. This reflects their desire to contribute to improving services and practices in their university and society. Some also shared that the internationalization experience has led to self-growth, which they can use to promote positive change in the university, culture, and country. As internationalization advocate, the participants saw themselves as promoters of internationalization activities. Having experienced firsthand the gains and challenges of global mobility, they believe that the experience has provided them the confidence and credibility to discuss internationalization's benefits. They saw themselves as internationalization spokespersons so that other students could join global mobility activities.

Based on the result, it is safe to say that the participants acknowledge that they have an essential role in the university as global mobility participants, which supports the idea posited by Robiños & Alcazaren (2023) that internationalization in education is a contributing factor toward quality culture in teaching and learning, and leadership and management. Interestingly, De Wit (2020) posited how some internationalization trends have changed over the years, leading to an increasing interest in internationalizing the curriculum at home instead of physical mobility, as it is often focused on the elite due to the cost of mobility programs.

To do these, they suggested some dissemination platforms, such as social media, oral presentations in classes and seminars, and personal sharing.

Participants' common dissemination plans

Themes	Sample Keywords/phrases	Frequency
1. Social media posting/blog	By posting on social media such as Instagram, YouTube, and blogs, write articles or blog posts detailing the professional skills acquired and the cultural insights gained	21
2. Classroom discussion and seminars	Seminars to share learnings, through workshops, storytelling, and digital content, Global Insights Forum, Mentorship Program ("Internationalization Fair")	21
3. Personal sharing	Share Filipino food with family, friends/classmates, teachers, leadership talks, and experience-sharing events that may inspire others, sharing information about different cultures, teaching methods, and communication skills	16
No answer		5
Total		63

Since social media is accessible and popular among young people and students, the participants saw it as an effective platform for reaching their intended audience and disseminating their experiences. These platforms include Facebook, Instagram, and blogs. Joining academic discussions in the classroom and participating in seminars was another dissemination platform. Some participants even suggested possible titles of workshops, such as the Global Insights Forum and Internationalization Fair. Lastly, they intend to share their experience with friends and colleagues. The participants still consider word-of-mouth as an effective means of disseminating information. One of the skills developed in internationalization is building meaningful connections, which widen a person's social circle. Therefore, personal sharing could be an effective means of disseminating internationalization experience.

Internationalization is a crucial aspect of higher education, preparing students for global challenges and opportunities. By fostering global connections, internationalization enables students to unlock their potential and make meaningful contributions to society.

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The growing emphasis on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has underscored the importance of global collaboration, including among students. As a result, policymakers recognize global mobility as a key driver of development, empowering students to become active participants in addressing global issues.

SMU's global mobility participants found their international experience invaluable to their academic journey, enhancing their personal growth through improved communication and social skills and boosting their professional development and educational formation. Ultimately, the skills and insights gained through internationalization enabled them to contribute meaningfully to the university.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Internationalization is an important component of education. It aids in personal and professional development so that the participants can become able members of society. This education component allows students to discover their hidden potential and global competencies.

This study found that global mobility participants see internationalization as a learning opportunity, a platform for building meaningful connections, cultural exchange, and establishing global affiliations. They are motivated to join internationalization to expand their horizons, meet new people, have a platform for discussing solutions to global issues, and out of curiosity.

The gains from internationalization are personal and academic growth, forging friendships and relationships, cultural awareness and appreciation, and flexibility. On the other hand, the challenges of internationalization include language barriers, cultural adaptation, and personal struggles. The participants appreciated international activities and organizers, the presence of buddies, and the non-academic support provided to make their stay comfortable and meaningful.

Lastly, they are willing and eager to use their experience to contribute to the betterment of other students, their university, and their country. They see themselves as a cultural bridge, agents of change, and internationalization advocates to inspire others to join global mobility activities.

It is therefore recommended that the university continue to expand its global linkages to support its internationalization initiatives. All units in the university must adopt an internationalization activity to ensure that the whole university is internationalized. Lastly, student support services for international students may be enhanced and articulated.

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Appendices

Informed Consent Form

This form is for participants in inbound and outbound global mobility activities of Saint Mary's University to participate in the research titled "Bridging Cultures, Expanding Horizons: Evaluating the Impact of Inbound and Outbound Mobility on Learning - Onward to a Robust Institutional Plan."

Name of Researchers Clara M. Gonzales (Lead)*
 Martin Gabriel Manuel (Primary Collaborator)
 Gerome Bautista (SMU)
 Katelijne Demeyere (Howest University, Belgium)
 Elly Verstraete (Vives University, Belgium)
 Dr. Jocelyn P. Carag (Education Supervisor II, CHED Region 2)

Organizational Affiliation* Saint Mary's University
 School of Teacher Education and Humanities
 Department of Languages
 Promotions, External Relations, and Internationalization Office

Information Sheet

You are being invited by faculty researchers from Saint Mary's University to participate in their study titled "Bridging Cultures, Expanding Horizons: Evaluating the Impact of Inbound and Outbound Mobility on Learning - Onward to a Robust Institutional Plan." Since your privacy is respectfully recognized, all information gathered will not be disclosed to anyone other than the researchers who are involved in the research study. All the data collected will be treated with utmost confidentiality following the Data Privacy Act. You will be assigned an alias/pseudonym to protect your identity. The accomplished interview will be kept in a personal cabinet accessible only to the researchers. The data will be kept for a period of one year, or once the University Research Center has given data clearance and approved the final study. The data will be disposed of by tearing the pages until the contents are no longer recognizable.

Your participation in this research study will contribute to developing knowledge on internationalization in higher educational institutions, which is essential for the achievement of the goals of the University. The results of this study will also help you make sense of your experiences during your mobility participation. Your participation, however, is optional and voluntary. You may participate in our study or decline anytime you feel uncomfortable. Should you decide not to participate, no questions will be asked, and you will not lose any benefit either.

Should you choose to participate in the study, your participation will take around 20-30 minutes to answer. You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements. There is, however, a possible health risk involved as the data gathering may be done face-to-face. To mitigate the risk, we assure you that we will comply with

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SMU's minimum health requirements. Also, should you experience psychological distress as a result of your participation, we will be more than happy to refer you to our Guidance counsellors (Cp.#: 0955-129-3356; Email: guidance@smu.edu.ph; Contact Person: Ms. Czarina Tubaran).

Even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue, and any information you have already provided will not be used in the study.

For any concerns related to the study, please contact the lead researcher:
 Clara M. Gonzales 09262110443 cgonzales@smu.edu.ph

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it, and any questions I have asked were answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to participate in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____ Date: _____

Interview Guide

Research Problems	Interview Guide Questions
1. What does internationalization mean to global mobility participants?	1. What does internationalization mean to you? 2. Why did you join global mobility activities?
2. How do global mobility participants view their experiences in internationalization?	3. What, for you, did you gain from your global mobility experience? Challenges? 4. What student services do you appreciate the most? What are your suggestions for better student services?
3. How do global mobility participants view the contribution of their experience to the University's culture of quality?	5. How do you see your role in the University as a global mobility participant? 6. How do you plan to disseminate/share your learnings from your global mobility experience? Any projects in mind?